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FATTY ACID COMPOSITION OF COMMON BUGLE HERB (*AJUGA REPTANS L.*)

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Мета. Ідентифікація та визначення якісного складу та кількісного вмісту жирних кислот у траві горлянки повзучої.

Методи дослідження. Дослідження жирних кислот горлянки повзучої проводили методом газової хромато-мас-спектрометрії, який заснований на утворенні метилових естерів жирних кислот з наступним їх визначенням.

Результати дослідження. Методом хромато-мас-спектрометрії вперше проведено вивчення жирнокислотного складу трави горлянки повзучої (*Ajugareptans L.*). В результаті дослідження в траві горлянки повзучої було виявлено 22 речовини, з них ідентифіковано - 9 жирних кислот. За кількісним вмістом переважали поліненасичені – ліноленова та ліолева жирні кислоти та насичені – пальмітинова. Їх загальний вміст в перерахунку на суму жирних кислот складав 56,71 % (ненасичені), 28,18 %- насичена. В незначній кількості виявлені – стеаринова, ейкозанова, тетракозанова, бегенова кислоти (6,65 %).

Висновки. Жирні кислоти є важливими біологічними компонентами, які беруть участь у складних метаболічних шляхах, є істотними компонентами ліпідів і клітинних мембран у вигляді фосфоліпідів, тим самим мають велику біологічну роль.

В траві горлянки повзучої в значній кількості містилися ненасичені жирні кислоти, вміст суми яких дорівнював 4706,78 мг/кг, що майже в 1,4 рази вище вмісту суми насичених жирних кислот (3380,83 мг/кг). Результати досліджень можуть бути використані при розробці методів контролю якості на сировину горлянки повзучої та одержанні біологічноактивних субстанцій з досліджуваної сировини

Ключові слова: горлянка повзуча, газова хромато-мас-спектрометрія, жирні кислоти, насичені кислоти, ненасичені кислоти

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1. Introduction

Ajuga reptans - perennial plant from the Lamiaceae family. The natural area of the bugle growth is quite widespread: throughout Europe, in the Mediterranean, Asia Minor, Central Asia, China, the Balkan Peninsula, as well as in Afghanistan and Iran, it is also found in North America. It grows in meadows and shrubs, in forest glade and forest edges [1, 2].

Many plants of *Ajuga* genus are used in traditional medicine as a remedy for fever, toothache, dysentery, malaria, high blood pressure, diabetes, gastrointestinal disorders as anthelmintic, diuretic and antifungal, anti-inflammatory and anti-mycobacterial agents [3]. Some of them also used as insect growth inhibitors. A large number of compounds have been isolated from plants of this genus, including phytoecdysteroids, diterpenoids, triter-

penes, sterols, anthocyanidin glucosides and iridoid glycosides, flavonoids, triglycerides and essential oils [4, 5].

Common bugle has not been used in official medicine. In the State Register of Medicines of Russia as an antitumor agent and an integral part of the mixture according to M. M. Zdrenko reported another species – *Ajuga Laxmannii* [6, 7]. Scientists also investigated the antiprotozoal effect of herbs extracts of this plant and its use in the treatment of malaria [8].

According to literary sources, N. Sahakyan et al (2010) studied the composition of fatty acids in other species of the *Ajuga* genus, namely, blue bugle (*Ajuga genevensis*) and Eastern bugle (*Ajuga orientalis*). These studies were conducted on samples of intact and callus plants. Six compounds were identified, including palmitic, stearic, oleic, linoleic, linolenic and arachidic fatty acids. The content of unsaturated fatty acids in callus plants grown in the autumn are predominant [9].

According to literary scientific sources, the use of common bugle in folk medicine is known. The bugle is used as an antiseptic, astringent, diaphoretic, wound healing, diuretic and antispasmodic agent, the plant improves metabolism, has a haemostatic effect [10]. The components of the plant help patients with various diseases: rheumatism, diseases of the gastrointestinal tract, diarrhea, pulmonary tuberculosis, inflammation of the appendages, cholelithiasis [11]. Effective use of the common bugle in case of inflammatory diseases of the oral cavity. The common bugle is known to contain volatile oil, tannins and traces of alkaloids. The chemical composition of the plant has been poorly studied, in particular, the fatty acid composition of the herb. It is known that fatty acids are involved in the biosynthesis of fats, metabolisms of hormones, are part of plant cells, have F-vitamin, immunopotentiating and antitumor action, reduce the level of cholesterol in the blood and activate fibrinolysis, regulate the activity of phospholipases, ion channels, information transfer, gene transcription [12, 13]. According to scientific data, polyunsaturated fatty acids play an important role in the prevention of coronary heart disease, which today came out on top among dangerous human diseases [14, 15].

The aim of the study was to conduct research to identify and quantify the content of fatty acids in the herb of the common bugle.

2. Planning (methodology) of research

Common bugle – plant used in folk medicine in many countries. The information on the composition of biologically active substances of the common bugle in the literature relates to raw materials growing in the East, Europe or the territory of Russia, at the same time there are no thorough studies of Ukrainian raw materials reserves [16, 17]. As we continue to work on common bugle in Ukraine, we have investigated its fatty acid composition. For the study of fatty acid composition, the method of gas chromatographic mass spectrometry was chosen, which is one of the most suitable methods for the

identification of multicomponent mixtures of volatile substances. The method is based on a combination of two separate methods - chromatography and mass spectrometry. The first is to separate the mixture into components, with the second to identify the substance and quantitative analysis [18, 19].

The quantitative content was determined by the internal standards method. The method of the internal standard has advantages, because when used it is not necessary to determine the complete composition of the mixture and the results of the analysis do not depend on the size of the sample [20].

3. Materials and methods

The object of study was a *Ajuga reptans* grass harvested during flowering (April-May) in the natural boundary v. Huta of Bohorodchany district of Ivano-Frankivsk region (48.65244 s.l., 24.21541 e.l.)

The fatty acid composition of the common bugle was studied by gas chromatography-mass spectrometry using an Agilent Technologies 6890 gas chromatograph with a 5973 mass spectrometry detector and an HP-5 ms capillary column with an internal diameter of 0.25 mm and a length of 30 m by the following method. In a flask of 20 ml was placed a sample of air-dry plant material, was added to the internal standard tridecane at a rate of 50 µg per sample, with subsequent calculation of the obtained concentration of the internal standard.

Chromatography conditions: chromatographic column – capillary HP- 5 ms (with internal diameter 0.25 mm, length 30 m), carrier gas velocity (helium) – 1.0 ml / min, temperature of the sample injection heater – 250 °C, temperature thermostat programmable from 60 to 320 °C at a speed of 7 deg / min.

To identify the components, the obtained spectra were considered on the basis of the general patterns of fragmentation of organic compounds by electron impact, as well as by comparing the results with the data of the mass spectra libraries NIST05 and WILEY 2007 with the total number of spectra more than 470000 in combination with programs for identification of AMDIS.

Quantitative content (X, mg / kg) was determined by the method of internal standards according to the formula:

$$X = \frac{P_1 \times 50}{P_2 \times m},$$

where P_1 – the peak area of the studied substance;
50 is the mass of the internal standard injected into the sample, µg;
 P_2 – peak area of the standard; m - sample of raw materials, g.

4. Results of the research

He results of the study of fatty acid composition in *Ajuga reptans* herb are shown in Fig. 1 and Table 1.

Fig. 1. Fatty acid chromatogram in *Ajuga reptans* herb:
1 – palmitic; 2 – linoleic; 3 – linolenic; 4 – stearic; 5 – peanut;
6 – behenic; 7 – tricosanoic; 8 – lignoceric; 9 – pentacosanoic.

Table 1

Qualitative composition and quantitative content of fatty acid composition of the studied *Ajuga reptans*

No.	The name of the substance	Systematic name IUPAC	Chemical formula	Retention time, min	Contents	
					mg/kg	%
1	Palmitic acid	hexadecanoic	C ₁₆ H ₃₂ O ₂	12.1	2338.25±0.01	21.18
2	Linoleic acid	cis,cis-9,12-octadecadienoic acid	C ₁₈ H ₃₂ O ₂	15.84	2133.11±0.04	25.70
3	α -Linolenic acid	cis,cis,cis-9,12,15-octadecatrienoic acid	C ₁₈ H ₃₀ O ₂	16	2573.67±0.04	31.01
4	Stearic acid	octadecanoic	C ₁₈ H ₃₆ O ₂	16.58	526.36±0.02	6.34
5	Arachidic acid	eicosanoic	C ₂₁ H ₄₁ O ₂	20.84	176.08±0.04	2.12
6	Behenic acid	docosanoic	C ₂₂ H ₄₄ O ₂	24.79	185.66±0.22	2.24
7	Tricosanoic acid	tricosanoic	C ₂₃ H ₄₆ O ₂	26.67	-	-
8	Lignoceric acid	tetracosanoic	C ₂₄ H ₄₈ O ₂	28.47	154.48±0.12	1.86
9	Pentacosanoic acid	pentacosanoic	C ₂₄ H ₄₉ O ₂	35.29	211.36±0.13	2.55
	Content of saturated fatty acids, %			56.71		
	Content of unsaturated fatty acids, %			43.29		
	Total, mg / kg			8298.96		

The obtained digital material was processed by the method of variational statistics using Student's t test.

5. Discussion

About 22 compounds were found in the *Ajuga reptans*, 9 of which were identified.

Out of the identified compounds, the highest concentration had polyunsaturated α -linolenic acid, the content of which was 2573.67 mg / kg of raw material or 31.01 % of the total content, saturated palmitic acid with a quantitative content of 2338.25 mg / kg or 21.18 % of the total content.

Also, the unsaturated linoleic acid was dominated by a content of 2133.11 mg / kg of raw material (25.70 % of all fatty acids of the bugle). The fatty acid composition was also represented by the glycerides of five fatty acids: stearic, arachidic, behenic, lignoceric, pentacosanoic. Thus, the value of the chemical composition of the raw material of the cervical neck is determined by the significant content of essential fatty acids, which play a number of important biological functions, which act as regulators of exchange processes, in particular, they participate in the lipid metabolism, affect the condition of the vessel wall, counteract the free radical oxidation.

Some of the compounds were not identified due to their lack in the library database.

Limitations of the study. A number of compounds were not identified during the study. The study is limited to the use of raw materials harvested from one site of growth and non-native plants.

Prospects for further research. The results of the study of the fatty acid composition of the above-ground part of the *Ajuga reptans* indicate the need for a more in-depth study of biologically active substances of this raw material. This raw material can be a promising source of medicines for both internal and external use.

6. Conclusions

In *Ajuga reptans* herb the qualitative and quantitative composition of fatty acids were determined with gas chromatography method.

In the studied raw material, 22 fatty acids were found, 9 of which were identified: among which 2 belong to unsaturated fatty acids, 7 to saturated ones.

In the *Ajuga reptans* herb, quantitative content was dominated by unsaturated fatty acids: α -linolenic acid and linoleic acid, and saturated fatty acids.

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